

ASSESSMENT OF CHALLENGES FACED IN ADOPTING DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTION BY CHEMISTRY TEACHERS IN NIGERIA

BY

AHMED Abiola Tawa¹, IBRAHIM Abdulmuhsin², ABIMBOLA Ahmatullahi Folakemi³ & ABDULRASAQ Bilikis Jimoh⁴

^{1,2&4}Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, AL-Hikmah, University, Ilorin, Nigeria.

³Department of Science Education, School of General Studies Education, Federal College of Education, Special, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Email: abdulmuhsinibrahim72@gmail.com

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Abstract

*Differentiated instruction (DI) is widely recognized as an effective pedagogical approach for addressing the diverse learning needs of students in contemporary classrooms. However, despite its potential benefits, many Chemistry teachers in Nigerian secondary schools encounter notable challenges in implementing it effectively. This study investigated the challenges faced by Chemistry teachers in applying differentiated instruction in Nigerian classrooms. A quantitative approach, specifically a descriptive cross-sectional survey, was adopted. The population comprised all Chemistry teachers in senior secondary schools in Nigeria, with a target population of 2,180 teachers drawn from six states in South-West Nigeria. A sample of 333 teachers was selected using a multistage sampling technique involving proportionate-to-size and simple random sampling to ensure representativeness. Data were collected using a validated questionnaire titled *Questionnaire on Nigerian Chemistry Teachers' Challenges on Differentiated Instruction*, which demonstrated a reliability coefficient of 0.76 using Cronbach's alpha. The data was analysed using mean and standard deviation. The findings indicated that teachers face challenges such as inadequate instructional resources, overcrowded classrooms, insufficient training, and limited time, all of which hinder effective implementation. The study recommends improved resource provision, enhanced professional development, and stronger institutional support to support DI practices.*

Keywords: *Differentiated instruction, time constraint, inadequate instructional resources, overcrowded classrooms*

Introduction

Nigeria's chemistry teachers were faced with many challenges due to the population increase of students in our educational system with different abilities (Abdulkadir & Ibrahim, 2025). A chemistry teacher is a type of science teacher who specializes in the discipline of chemistry. Chemistry is practically applied in all activities of daily existence, which gives an integral understanding of the natural world around us. However, the dilemma of chemistry as a subject has long garnered attention among chemistry educators to reform chemistry education. It is a challenge for the teacher to think of appropriate teaching strategies that will be suitable for individual student needs and learning styles. The teacher is responsible

for teaching many aspects of the chemical properties of substances, as well as the processes that they undergo under a wide variety of circumstances. These chemistry teachers are familiar with the use of a number of teaching methods, but more especially the conventional methods like lecture, discussion and demonstration methods. Although in a traditional chemistry classroom, a teacher presents information in a lecture style, which provides each student with the same laboratory investigation. This approach is often more suitable for learners who possess sustained attention and higher-order logical and analytical thinking skills, consistent with findings from John Sweller's cognitive load

theory, which emphasizes the role of cognitive capacity in learning effectiveness (Chen et al., 2025). But unfortunately, only a few of the students are good at these aspects.

According to Sedeño et al. (2021), students suffered much in chemistry, like in other academic subjects, because students' diversity was not addressed. Hence, instruction based on the idea of one-size-fits-all is not appropriate for subjects like chemistry when considering the importance of technological development of Nigeria as a nation. The use of appropriate strategies that will offer options that will meet the needs of all the students, ensuring that everyone is achieving the same learning objective. The use of differentiated instruction is a feasible and optimistic option for educators at all levels. According to Spyropoulou et al. (2025), the creation of lesson plans, projects, laboratory activities, assessments and learning environments to accommodate the individual readiness, interest and learning profile of each student is the basic idea for differentiation.

Differentiated instruction is a method of teaching that provides students with a range of entry points to access learning that is compatible with their way of understanding (Gheysens et al., 2023). As a result of this, not all students are the same; teaching and assessment methods must change in order to avoid teaching only a group of students, and the slow learners will be left behind. Liou et al. (2023) asserted that when teachers accommodate students' differences, especially their readiness, levels, interests, and learning profiles, students learn at their best. Differentiated instruction is a system that provides students with different avenues for acquiring course content so that all the students within a classroom can learn effectively, regardless of differences in ability and provides a framework for modifying curriculum and teaching strategies to complement the knowledge of readiness, area of interest and learning profiles.

Gal et al. (2025) noted that classrooms are becoming more diverse. Due to educational trends across the globe, with the increase in the population of students for three or more decades now. Classrooms are filled with students who have different needs, come from different educational backgrounds, have different attention spans, have different language abilities and have different cultural backgrounds. As a result of students with different needs, different backgrounds, educators have been intrigued and challenge by the diversity of student in the classroom, but could not find solution to student varied needs instead, they rely on teaching the whole size with one approach, expecting all the students to do same activity, work at the same pace, do the same homework, and answer the question in the test items. This resulted in frustration on the part of many students who find the work unchallenging and boring. On the part of the teacher, they felt they were not reaching every student; in view of this, many teachers have discovered that they can better meet the diverse needs of their students by using differentiated instruction (Langelaan et al., 2024).

According to Zahid and Nawab (2025), the diversity in students' needs, learning styles, experiences, and interests has led educators to re-examine their teaching and instructional practices with a view to ascertaining a better approach to teaching and learning that will give students multiple options for taking in information and making sense of ideas given by the teacher. As a result of this, differentiated instruction was invented to cater for a variety of learning profiles. Differentiated instruction is a way of thinking about teaching and learning which involved creating multiple parts for students with different abilities, interests or learning styles. According to Pozas et al. (2022), noted that differentiated instruction is a way by which the teacher anticipates the differences in the student readiness, interests, and learning profiles, as a result of this the teacher create different

learning paths that student will have the opportunity to learn as much as they can, without any anxiety or because the assignments are too taxing or boredom since they are not challenging enough. Smale-Jacobse et al. (2019) define differentiated instruction simply as providing instruction in a diversity of approaches to meet the needs of various learners. This allows students to take greater responsibility and ownership of their own learning, and it provides opportunities for cooperative learning to take place.

Although differentiated instruction has been widely acknowledged for its potential to enhance students' learning, its practical implementation in Chemistry classrooms remains a significant challenge. This difficulty arises because Chemistry teachers are required to simultaneously address diverse learners' needs while maintaining effective lesson planning and delivery within limited instructional time. In addition, the successful application of differentiated instruction demands specialized pedagogical skills, adequate instructional support, and access to appropriate resources, which are often insufficient in many school contexts. These constraints make it difficult for teachers to translate the theoretical benefits of differentiated instruction into actual classroom practice. Consequently, despite its recognized value, the gap between the expected outcomes of differentiated instruction and its real-world application continues to pose a major concern, thereby necessitating a systematic investigation into the specific challenges faced by Chemistry teachers.

Theoretical framework

The theory that underpins this differentiated instruction strategy is Vygotsky (1978), the principles of constructivism (Vygotsky, 1978) and Bloom's taxonomy (Kojak, 2008). Accordingly, differentiated instruction employs multiple teaching entries, educational activities and tasks, and varies between group

and individual learning, and small and cooperative groups (Desinguraj & Ebenezer, 2021). According to Kojak (2008), the psychologist's attempts in integrating the set of social and psychological theories into differentiated instruction aim at bringing the learner to the ultimate level of learning and balanced growth. Vygotsky believes that the mind of the learner grows and develops through exposure to new experiences that challenge his abilities and level of thinking; the new conflicting learning context prompts the learner to create solutions and assimilate the new knowledge into his prior experiences (Tomlinson, 1995). As a result of this, the teaching of chemistry should be done by the teachers using differentiated instruction to cater to all the students in the classroom based on their needs, interests, and learning profiles. PCK play a vital role in a teacher's ability to differentiate instruction (Salleh et al., 2022), and the lack of PCK will adversely affect a teacher's ability to be flexible with the delivery of content and adapt to the individual needs of students (Shi et al., 2025).

Catering to student needs

A fundamental responsibility of a chemistry teacher is to design instruction that aligns with how students learn best, especially given the abstract and intellectually demanding nature of many chemistry concepts. Classrooms typically consist of learners with varied prior knowledge, levels of motivation, and preferred learning styles. When a single, uniform teaching method is applied, it often leads to uneven understanding, reduced engagement, and lower academic performance. This underscores the need for differentiated instruction as a strategic approach to accommodate learner diversity and improve learning outcomes. As noted by Silverman (2024), effective teaching in a differentiated classroom requires adapting instruction to students' readiness, interests, and learning profiles to ensure that tasks are both

meaningful and appropriately challenging. Adjusting instruction based on readiness enables teachers to align learning activities with students' current levels of understanding through approaches such as tiered tasks, varied assessments, and learning contracts (Silverman, 2024). This is particularly crucial in chemistry, where students often differ in their grasp of foundational concepts. In addition, incorporating students' interests such as their personal inclinations and areas of curiosity can significantly enhance motivation and active participation. Strategies like group investigations, interest-based activities, and multiple intelligence approaches help make learning more engaging and relevant. Moreover, considering learners' profiles ensures that teaching methods reflect how students best process information, whether through collaboration, analytical reasoning, or creative expression (Bani, 2020). The justification for this approach is further supported by the need to foster inclusive learning environments that cater to all students, including those who excel and those who require additional support. Gifted learners, for instance, may benefit from more independent and advanced tasks, while others may need guided instruction. Therefore, effective chemistry teaching involves intentionally modifying content, instructional processes, expected outputs, and the learning environment to meet both the academic and emotional needs of students, ultimately improving understanding and participation (Kanapathy, 2023).

Lesson plan and Delivery

For effective learning to take place, there must be an adequate lesson plan prepared by the teachers (Achimugu et al., 2025). One of the major challenges that teachers face in differentiated instruction is preparation for lesson plans and delivery. Lesson planning is the activity which the teacher performs before

the actual lesson takes place (Achimugu et al., 2025).

A lesson plan is a detailed description of the instructional strategies and learning activities to be performed by the teacher during the teaching/ learning process. An effective differentiated instruction classroom, it requires more sophisticated and highly specialised instruction methods; teachers need adequate training, mentoring and professional development to ensure that they are using differentiated instructional techniques appropriately and effectively. Most teachers argue that the practical realities of using this type of instructional method are not feasible, especially in large classes comprising students with a wide range of abilities. As a result of this, chemistry teachers find it difficult to prepare a lesson plan that will be useful for students with a variety of abilities. Onyishi and Sefotho (2020) identify several key components that teachers could use as a guide in differentiation in the education environment, which teachers may differentiate instruction: content, process, product and affect/ environment.

Support and skills

In the differentiated instruction classroom chemistry teacher are faced with challenges of use of different materials which can be used to bring about effective delivery of instruction in the classroom. The chemistry teachers find it difficult to implement the DI because they are unable to change their usual method of teaching, which they are already used to, for example, the traditional method of teaching. Papanthymou and Darra (2022) analysed the factors that affect teachers' difficulties in the process of implementing differentiated instructional strategies. Teacher's teaching experience is one of the major factors that affect the implementation of DI (Shareefa, 2023). As a result, teachers with less experience may not have the experience that enables them to implement DI in the

classroom. Also, the support team, such as school administrators (principals, head teachers) and co-teachers, would make a significant impact and provide the support they needed, which can assist with the process of implementing DI methods. Hence, for effective implementation of DI, the teachers should work as a team in order to achieve the expected result of using DI. Teachers are a significant contributor to the process of implementing and using DI. As a result of this, the administrators should understand and receive training so that they can assist teachers and improve their practice (Nagdaparan & Nagdaparan, 2025).

However, Adeniran et al. (2025) believe that better-trained teachers on the application of differentiated instruction as a result of in-service training, coupled with support from other teachers in the classrooms, will find the application of DI less challenging. It is also logical to think that less experienced or newly employed teachers might apply differentiated instruction more than peers with longer experience; this is under the assumption that novice teachers might be more motivated to put the most up-to-date techniques and strategies into practice in order to be 21st-century teachers. For effective usage of DI, the chemistry teacher should have the skills needed to implement the DI successfully in the classroom. The skills needed by teachers are ability by the ability of chemistry teachers to differentiate according to students' needs based on individual differences. Teachers need to be aware that all students' needs also extend to the gifted and special needs students (Ahmad et al., 2023). Putri et al. (2024) noted that there was a strong need for teachers to have extensive training in the implementation of DI. Chemistry teachers have not been trained on how to use DI extensively, hence this has contributed to a major challenge of DI implementation in the classroom.

Time Constraints

The time allocated for instruction in the classroom is very small when considering the implementation of differentiated instruction. Chemistry lessons usually can be double period, which lasts for a maximum of one hour and twenty minutes, which is normally used for practical. The time would not be favourable for the effective delivery of DI. Teachers' options are beliefs about DI is that the use of DI makes students to be motivated and enthusiastic about learning (Ojelade, 2024). One of the factors that hindered them from using DI in the classroom was time constraints. The DI lessons are time-consuming because the teachers require more planning time and more analysis time, so that all cannot get done effectively within the allocated time on the school timetable. The demands of time for planning and preparation are a major concern for teachers (Farisia et al., 2025).

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study was to identify the challenges faced by Chemistry Teachers when practising differentiated instruction in classrooms in Nigeria. Specifically, this study aimed to:

1. Determine the challenges faced by chemistry teachers in practising DI
2. Identify the challenges faced by chemistry teachers as regard students' needs when practising DI
3. Examine the skills needed by Chemistry teachers when practising DI
4. Determine the time constraint encountered by chemistry teachers when practising DI

Classroom

Research Questions

1. What are the challenges facing Chemistry Teachers in practising the DI classroom?

2. What are the challenges faced by chemistry teachers as regard students' needs when **practicing** DI?
3. What are the challenges faced by chemistry teachers as regards to skills needed to acquire when **practicing** the DI classroom in Nigeria?
4. What are the time constraints faced by chemistry teachers when practising DI?

Research Method

The study employed a quantitative approach using a descriptive survey design of the cross-sectional type. This design was considered appropriate for collecting quantitative data through questionnaires from a large population at a single point in time in order to identify the challenges faced by Chemistry teachers in implementing differentiated instruction in Nigerian classrooms. The cross-sectional survey approach also enabled the generalization of findings from a representative sample to the wider population.

The population of the study comprised all Chemistry teachers teaching in senior secondary schools in Nigeria, with a target population of 2,180 Chemistry teachers across the six states in South-West Nigeria, namely Ekiti, Lagos, Ogun, Ondo, Osun, and Oyo States. The sample consisted of 333 Chemistry teachers selected from the target population based on the sample size determination table by Cohen et al. (2018) at a 95% confidence level and a $\pm 5.0\%$ margin of error.

A multistage sampling procedure was adopted to ensure adequate representation of Chemistry teachers across the six states and to enhance the validity and generalizability of the findings. Proportionate-to-size sampling was first used to distribute the sample across the states according to the population of teachers

in each state, thereby ensuring fair representation. This was followed by simple random sampling to select individual participants, giving each teacher an equal chance of selection and minimizing sampling bias. In addition, purposive sampling was employed to ensure that only teachers currently teaching Chemistry in government-approved senior secondary schools were included in the study. Data were collected using a researcher-developed questionnaire titled *Questionnaire on Nigerian Chemistry Teachers' Challenges on Differentiated Instruction*, which utilized a four-point Likert scale with a benchmark mean of 2.50.

The instrument was validated by experts, including a science educator, a senior Chemistry teacher, and a specialist in measurement and evaluation, to ensure its content, construct, and face validity. Their suggestions were incorporated into the final version of the instrument. A trial testing was conducted with 50 Chemistry teachers outside the study area, and the internal consistency of the instrument was established using Cronbach's alpha, which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.76, indicating acceptable reliability. Approval was obtained from school principals before data collection commenced. The questionnaire was administered both physically by the researchers and trained assistants and electronically through Google Forms to reach participants who were not accessible in person.

Ethical standards were strictly observed throughout the study. Participants were adequately informed about the purpose and procedures of the study, and their informed consent was obtained prior to participation. They were assured of confidentiality, voluntary participation, and the right to withdraw at any stage without any

consequences. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics, with research questions addressed through the computation of mean and standard deviation

using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0.

Result and Interpretations

Research Question one: *What are the challenges facing Chemistry Teachers in practising the DI classroom?*

Table 1: Mean response on the *are the challenges facing Chemistry Teachers in practising the DI classroom?*

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	ST.D
1.	I find it difficult to implement differentiated instruction due to large class sizes.	3.28	0.72
2.	Limited instructional resources hinder my ability to practice differentiated instruction effectively.	3.34	0.68
3.	I experience difficulty in managing diverse learners during differentiated instruction.	3.22	0.75
4.	Inadequate training prevents me from effectively applying differentiated instruction strategies.	3.30	0.70
5.	The lack of institutional support affects my use of differentiated instruction in the classroom.	3.26	0.73
Grand Mean		3.26	

The findings presented in Table 1 show that Chemistry teachers generally acknowledged multiple factors as significant obstacles to the effective implementation of differentiated instruction in the classroom, as indicated by the grand mean of 3.26, which exceeds the acceptance benchmark of 2.50. Among these, inadequate instructional resources (Mean = 3.34, SD = 0.68) and insufficient training (Mean = 3.30, SD = 0.70) emerged as the most critical issues, reflecting limitations in both material provision and professional competence. Other notable challenges include large class sizes (Mean = 3.28, SD = 0.72) and weak institutional support (Mean = 3.26, SD =

0.73), which point to broader systemic and organizational constraints. Furthermore, the difficulty associated with managing learners of diverse abilities (Mean = 3.22, SD = 0.75) underscores the practical complexities encountered within the classroom environment. The relatively small standard deviation values suggest a reasonable level of consensus among respondents, indicating that these challenges are widely experienced. Overall, the results highlight that both structural conditions and instructional limitations continue to impede the effective application of differentiated instruction in Chemistry classrooms.

Research Question Two: *What are the challenges faced by chemistry teachers as regard students' needs when practising DI?*

Table 2: **Mean response of challenges faced by chemistry teachers as regard students' needs when practising DI?**

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	ST.D
1.	I Cater for students needs by motivating them based on their interest	3.41	0.65
2.	Different methods and materials were needed to be used in differs classroom	3.36	0.69

3.	Effective learning can take place when teachers differentiate according to students readiness	3.39	0.66
4.	Effective learning can take place when teachers differentiated based on interest and learning profile	3.44	0.63
5.	The teacher should be able to differentiate the instruction based on the content, process and product	3.47	0.61
Grand Mean		3.40	

The findings in Table 2 indicate that Chemistry teachers expressed strong agreement on the need to consider students' diverse characteristics when implementing differentiated instruction, as reflected by a grand mean of 3.40, which exceeds the accepted benchmark of 2.50. The item with the highest mean score differentiating instruction based on content, process, and product (Mean = 3.47, SD = 0.61) highlights the importance of adopting flexible teaching approaches to accommodate varying learner needs. In a similar vein, attention to students' interests and learning profiles (Mean = 3.44, SD = 0.63), as well as motivating learners based on their

interests (Mean = 3.41, SD = 0.65), were strongly supported, emphasizing the relevance of learner-centered instructional practices. Additionally, adapting instruction to students' readiness levels (Mean = 3.39, SD = 0.66) and employing diverse teaching methods and materials (Mean = 3.36, SD = 0.69) were identified as key factors in promoting effective learning. The relatively low standard deviation values suggest a high degree of consensus among respondents. Overall, the results imply that the effectiveness of differentiated instruction is closely tied to teachers' capacity to acknowledge and address individual differences in students' readiness, interests, and learning preferences.

Research Question Three: *What are the challenges faced by chemistry teachers as regards to skills needed to acquire when practising the DI classroom in Nigeria?*

Table 3: Mean Response of *the challenges faced by chemistry teachers as regards to skills needed to acquire when practising the DI classroom in Nigeria?*

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	ST.D
1.	School heads and owners do not provide adequate facilities to teach the student effectively based on DI.	3.25	0.74
2.	We lack fund to acquire more facilities that will assist the students.	3.31	0.71
3.	I do find it more difficult to implement acquired skills in my teaching using DI.	3.18	0.76
4.	Differentiated instruction needs different teaching skills and method of application to students therefore, I find it difficult to use these skills effectively.	3.27	0.72
5.	Inadequate support from the government do not encourage the effective teaching using DI in classroom.	3.33	0.69
Grand Total		3.27	

The findings presented in Table 3 show that Chemistry teachers generally agreed that challenges related to skill acquisition and insufficient institutional support hinder the

effective implementation of differentiated instruction, as indicated by a grand mean of 3.27, which exceeds the benchmark of 2.50. Prominent concerns include inadequate

government support (Mean = 3.33, SD = 0.69) and limited funding for acquiring essential facilities (Mean = 3.31, SD = 0.71), underscoring the importance of external support mechanisms in promoting effective DI practices. Likewise, the inadequacy of facilities provided by school authorities (Mean = 3.25, SD = 0.74) reflects constraints within the school system. Regarding teachers' competencies, respondents reported challenges in effectively applying differentiated instruction skills (Mean = 3.27, SD = 0.72) and

difficulty in translating acquired skills into classroom practice (Mean = 3.18, SD = 0.76), indicating gaps in practical proficiency. The relatively low standard deviation values suggest a consistent pattern of responses among participants. Overall, the results indicate that limitations in professional capacity, coupled with insufficient financial and institutional support, significantly impede the successful implementation of differentiated instruction in Chemistry classrooms

Research Question four: *What are the time constraints faced by chemistry teachers when practising DI?*

Table 4: Mean Response on *time constraints faced by chemistry teachers when practising DI?*

S/N	ITEMS	MEAN	ST.D
1.	The time allotted for chemistry lesson lower the performance of DI instruction in the class room.	3.35	0.68
2.	The time demands for planning of lesson in DI classroom is one of the major problems faced by the teachers.	3.38	0.66
3.	For effective delivery lesson in DI classroom the teacher beliefs that student needs to be motivated	3.21	0.73
4.	I used more time for planning because time allocated for chemistry lesson on school time table is not appropriate.	3.33	0.70
5.	I perceive inadequate time affect chemistry teachers in delivery of DI in the classroom.	3.37	0.67
	Grand Mean 3.33	3.33	

The findings presented in Table 4 show that Chemistry teachers generally agreed that time-related constraints the effective implementation of differentiated instruction, as indicated by the grand mean of 3.33, which is above the benchmark value of 2.50. The major concerns identified include the considerable time required for lesson planning and preparation (Mean = 3.38, SD = 0.66) and the perception that insufficient time negatively impacts instructional delivery (Mean = 3.37, SD = 0.67), highlighting the demanding nature of DI practices. Furthermore, limited instructional time allocated for Chemistry lessons (Mean = 3.35, SD = 0.68) and the need

for additional planning time due to unsuitable timetable arrangements (Mean = 3.33, SD = 0.70) point to systemic scheduling challenges within schools. The need to motivate and engage students for effective instruction (Mean = 3.21, SD = 0.73), though slightly lower, also reflects the influence of time on instructional effectiveness. The relatively small standard deviation values indicate a fair level of consistency in the responses of participants. Overall, the results suggest that inadequate instructional time, coupled with the demanding nature of lesson preparation, poses the effective use of differentiated instruction in Chemistry classroom

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the present study reveal that Chemistry teachers generally perceive

differentiated instruction (DI) as being hindered by a combination of interconnected challenges, including limited instructional resources, inadequate teacher preparedness, large and diverse classrooms, and insufficient instructional time. The overall mean scores, which were above the decision benchmark, indicate a general consensus among respondents that these factors the effective implementation of DI. In particular, the results highlight those overcrowded classrooms, lack of adequate teaching materials, and limited institutional and governmental support pose substantial barriers to practice. While teachers acknowledged the importance of addressing students' varying readiness levels, interests, and learning profiles through flexible instructional approaches, many reported difficulties in translating this awareness into practice due to insufficient training and lack of support systems. Additionally, time-related constraints, especially the limited time available for lesson planning and classroom instruction, were found to significantly impede the effective use of differentiated instructional strategies in Chemistry classrooms.

The findings of this study indicate that time constraint is a major challenge to the effective implementation of differentiated instruction (DI) among chemistry teachers. This aligns with existing literature that consistently identifies time pressure as one of the most significant barriers to successful differentiation in classroom practice. For example, Farisia et al. (2025) and Ojelade (2024) noted that DI demands considerable time for planning lessons, developing varied instructional materials, and providing individualized student support requirements that often exceed the time allocated within standard school timetables. This supports the

present finding that teachers struggle to reconcile curriculum coverage with the additional time demands of differentiated instruction.

In a similar vein, the views of Onyishi and Sefotho (2020) and Goyibova et al. (2025) emphasize that effective differentiation requires continuous planning, adjustment of teaching strategies, and ongoing assessment of learners, all of which are highly time-consuming processes. The current study reflects this reality, as many chemistry teachers reported insufficient time to design tiered tasks, modify instructional content, and assess students individually due to rigid lesson schedules.

Additionally, the findings are consistent with studies that highlight the compounding effect of large class sizes and heavy workloads on teachers' available time. Langelaan et al. (2024) observed that increasing learner diversity requires more individualized attention, which further increases time demands on teachers. This aligns with the present study, where participants indicated that short lesson periods and large student populations significantly limit their ability to address individual learning needs effectively.

Overall, the study concludes that although differentiated instruction is widely recognized as an effective teaching approach, its implementation in chemistry classrooms is largely constrained by inadequate instructional time. This creates a clear gap between policy expectations and classroom realities, suggesting that meaningful improvement will require structural interventions such as more flexible timetabling, reduced teacher workload, and stronger institutional support systems.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study established that Chemistry teachers in Nigerian senior secondary schools recognize differentiated instruction as a valuable approach for addressing students' diverse learning needs; however, its effective implementation is significantly constrained by several interrelated challenges, including inadequate instructional resources, large class sizes, limited professional training, insufficient institutional support, and time constraints. While teachers demonstrated an awareness of the need to adapt instruction based on students' readiness, interests, and learning profiles, the findings revealed a gap between this awareness and actual classroom practice due to systemic and contextual limitations. The study therefore underscores the necessity for targeted interventions such as continuous professional development, provision of adequate teaching resources, reduced class sizes, and stronger administrative support to enhance teachers' capacity to effectively implement differentiated instruction and improve student learning outcomes in Chemistry.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following were recommended:

1. School authorities and policymakers should provide adequate instructional materials, reduce class sizes, and create enabling teaching environments to minimize these constraints.
2. Chemistry teachers should regularly assess learners' readiness, interests, and learning profiles and employ flexible teaching strategies that align instruction with these diverse needs.
3. Educational authorities should organize regular professional development programmes and provide continuous administrative and peer support to equip Chemistry teachers with the necessary competencies for effective DI implementation.
4. School management should adjust timetables and allocate sufficient instructional and planning time to enable Chemistry teachers to effectively design and deliver differentiated instruction in the classroom.

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